

Synthesis, characterization and thermal studies of cresol based polyphosphate esters

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Abstract : Polyphosphate esters were synthesized from cresol phosphorodichloridates and dihydric phenols by interfacial polycondensation using a phase transfer catalyst. The polymers were characterized by IR, ^1H and ^{31}P NMR spectroscopy and GPC. The thermal stability of the polymers was determined by thermogravimetry.

Keywords : Phosphorodichloridates, polyphosphate, thermal stability, PTC catalyst.

Introduction

Phosphorous-containing polymers have received considerable attention in the recent past owing to their effectiveness as flame retardants¹. The most important method for the synthesis of polyphosphates is the esterification of alkyl or aryl phosphorodichloridates with diols or dihydric phenols. The polymerization is usually carried out by melt, solution or interfacial condensation.

Cardanol based polyphosphate esters have been synthesized and characterised² before by one of the authors. This article reports the synthesis of a series of polyphosphate esters based on aryl phosphorodichloridates of *ortho*, *meta* and *para* cresols with dihydric phenols such as bisphenol and phenolphthalein by an interfacial polycondensation using a phase transfer catalyst. The polymers were characterized by IR, ^1H and ^{31}P NMR spectroscopy. The molecular weights of the polymers were determined by gel permeation chromatography. The thermal stability of the polymers was studied by thermogravimetry.

Experimental

POCl_3 , AlCl_3 , NaOH , cresols, bisphenol, phenolphthalein, CHCl_3 , hexane, hexamethylenetetramine, Aliquat 336 and all other chemicals used were of analytical grade. The transmission infrared spectra were recorded on Thermo-Nicollet Avatar 370 model. ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on Hitachi R-24B high-resolution NMR spectrometer in CDCl_3 using TMS as internal reference. ^{31}P NMR spectra were recorded on a JEOL FX-90 QFT spectrometer. The GPC data were obtained using Hewlett-

Packard 1081 B HPLC, equipped with an automatic sample injection system and a differential RI detector. GPC columns used were styrene-divinyl benzene copolymers based microstyragel 100 Å, 500 Å and 1000 Å (Waters Associates) connected in series. THF (HPLC grade) was used as the eluent. The thermo gravimetric studies were carried out on a Dupont thermo gravimetric analyzer model 951 in nitrogen and air atmospheres at a heating rate of $15\text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$ with a sample weight of 5–8 mg.

The aryl phosphorodichloridates were prepared from POCl_3 and the corresponding phenols³ as in Scheme 1. A pinch of aluminum chloride and POCl_3 (0.1 mol) were taken in 30 ml dry hexane in a 250 ml 2-necked R.B. flask fitted with a reflux condenser and separating funnel

Scheme 1

placed on a magnetic stirrer. The corresponding phenol (0.1 mol) in 60 ml dry hexane was added dropwise and refluxed for 30 min. Solvent was distilled out. Typical procedure for the synthesis of polyphosphate ester from aryl phosphorodichloridate and dihydric phenol is given below. Bisphenol (0.01 mol) and aqueous NaOH (6 g in 200 ml) were taken in a 500 ml R.B. flask. To this 2 weight % of Aliquat 336 (Tricapryl methyl ammonium chloride) was added and stirred magnetically. A solution of aryl phosphorodichloridate (0.015 mol) in 50 ml dry chloroform was added to the stirring mixture and the reaction continued for another 10 min (Scheme 2). The chloroform layer was separated and poured into large quantity of methanol to precipitate the polymer. The precipitation was repeated 2–3 times to remove the low molecular weight fraction. The polymer was dried at room temperature.

Scheme 2

Condensation polymerization with HMTA : Polyphosphate esters prepared as above was heated with 10% HMTA at 80–120 °C for 1 h. The cresol based esters resulted in a highly viscous yellowish resin whereas phenol based esters gave rise to harder solid residues with orange red colour indicating the greater extent of crosslinking in the latter.

Results and discussion

A series of polyphosphate esters (polymers I–VI) were prepared from the phosphorodichloridates of different cresols and phenol with dihydric phenols such as bisphenol and phenolphthalein by an interfacial polycondensation reaction using Aliquat 336 as catalyst as illustrated in Scheme 2. The polymerization proceeded rapidly with yields in the range 80–90%. The M_n values of the polyphosphates range from 1100 to 2500 with polydispersities varying from 1.7 to 3.9 (Table 1).

Table 1. Yield and molecular weights of the polymers

Polymer	Yield	M_n	M_w	$M_w/M_n = D$
I	90	1150	3910	3.4
II	80	1450	4090	2.8
III	85	1100	3520	3.2
IV	88	1560	4660	3.0
V	84	2000	5350	2.7
VI	80	1900	5470	2.9

The characteristic IR absorption frequencies of the polymers were similar and are given in Table 2. The polymers exhibited absorption peaks at 1235 cm^{-1} corresponding to the P=O stretching vibration. The absorptions at 960 cm^{-1} indicate P–O–C aromatic stretching vibrations. The ^1H NMR chemical shift values of the polymers are given in Table 3. The multiplet in the region δ 6.6 to 7.1 corresponds to the aromatic protons of the arylphosphorodichloridate and the corresponding dihydric phenols. The peaks in the region δ 1.0 to 2.0 correspond to the aliphatic protons present in bisphenol and cresol. The ^{31}P NMR spectra of the polymers show signals at around δ 18.0 corresponding to the P in the repeat unit and at around δ 12.0 corresponding to P at the chain end. Thermal stabilities are presented in Table 4. The parameters studied are T_i - initial decomposition temperature, $T_{1/2}$ - temperature at which 50% decomposition

Table 2. Infrared absorption frequencies of the polyphosphates (wave number cm^{-1})

1	2	3	4	5	6		
682 (m)	685 (w)	680 (w)	675 (m)	680 (w)	685 (w)	C-H	Def.
960 (m)	950 (m)	965 (w)	960 (w)	955 (m)	960 (m)	P-O-C	Str.
1221 (m)	1235 (s)	1230 (s)	1235 (s)	1230 (s)	1230 (s)	P=O	Str.
1462 (s)	C=C	Str.					
-	-	-	-	1756 (s)	1756 (s)	C=O	Str.
2852 (m)	2850 (m)	2860 (m)	2870 (m)	2860 (m)	2860 (m)	C-H	Str.
2966 (s)	P-O-H	Str.					
3056 (w)	3056 (w)	3050 (w)	3048 (w)	3048 (w)	3048 (w)	C-C	Str.

Table 3. ^1H NMR spectral data for *m*-cresol bisphenol polyphosphate

δ (ppm)	Description of peaks
1.2 (6H, s)	Two CH_3 of bisphenol
2.0 (3H, s)	Benzyl protons
6.7 (4H, m)	Aromatic protons of <i>m</i> -cresol
7.2 (8H, m)	Aromatic protons of bisphenol

Table 4. Thermal stabilities of the polyphosphates

Polymer	T_i	$T_{1/2}$	T_{max}	% char yield	% P content
I	284.87	435	506.75	38	8.15
II	247.41	398	410.64	19	8
III	235.13	356	495.65	16	7.5
IV	295.28	450	515.56	40	8.5
V	291.42	440.87	510.45	39	6.59
VI	305.36	468.79	520.78	43	6.79

occurs, T_{max} - temperature at which maximum rate of weight loss occurs and C_y - char yield at 500 °C. These polymers are stable in the temperature range 230–310 °C in nitrogen atmosphere. As $T_{1/2}$ was found more reliable than T_i in interpreting thermal stability in relation to char yield, $T_{1/2}$ was taken as the criteria of thermal stability for

the present study. Comparison of the values given in Table 4 shows that among the first four polymers polymer IV is the most stable ($T_{1/2}$ 450 °C, C_y 40). Thermal stability of polymer IV may be due to the loss of labile CH_3 group in the side chain of the cresol based esters. Polymers V and VI are derived from phenolphthalein, whose structural rigidity might be contributing to its stability. The comparatively high phosphorous content in polymer IV (8.5%) might also contribute to its higher $T_{1/2}$ value (450 °C) and char yield (40). It is also clear that the thermal stability of these polymers is directly related to char yield. Thus our observation is in conformity with the previous reports in this field.

References

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